

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 AND TEACHER EDUCATION

Prof. Gautami V. Kamble

Assistant Professor (Dept. Of Geography)

Karmveer Hire College, Gargoti,

Tal - Bhudargad, Dist – Kolhapur

Abstract:

The National Education policy has strong political will and deep commitment to the universalisation of elementary education. Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential developing in a society & promoting national development education policy are most essential for the leadership of the global stage it terms of economic growth, social justice and equality. New education policy 2020 deals with rural & urban areas development of education particularly SC,ST, NT, OBC & Deprived classes in our country. In this way new education policy 2020 most important in our developing country as well as to education of training for teacher's faculty members, students, parents, etc.

Keyword: *National Education Policy 2020, Teacher Education, suggestions etc.*

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Introduction:

Education is a fundamental for achieving full human potential developing an equitable and just society and promoting national development. Providing universal access to quality education is the key to India's continued ascent, and leadership on the global stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality, scientific advancement national integration and cultural preservation universal high-quality education is the best way forward for developing and maximizing our country's rich talents and resources for the good of the individual ,the society ,the country ,and the world .India will have the highest population of young people in the world over the next decade and our ability to provide high-quality educational opportunities to them will determine the future of our country.

This National Education policy 2020 is the first education policy of 21st century and aims to address the many growing development imperatives of our country .This policy proposes the revision and revamping of all aspects of the education structure ,including its regulation and governance to create a new system that is aligned with the aspirational goals of 21st century education including SDG ,while building upon India's traditions and value system The National Education Policy lays particular emphasis on the development of the creative potential of each Individual. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive Capacities. Both the foundational capacities of literacy and numeracy and higher -order cognitive capacities, such as critical thinking and problem solving.

Objective of Study:

- i. To study the present position of the teacher education
- ii. To study the new education policy 2020 in the reference of the teacher education

Research Methodology:

A Researcher has used secondary data collected from various books, Journals, Magazine, and website etc.

Hypothesis:

- i. Present position of the Teacher Education is very complicated & critical.
- ii. New Educational policy 2020 ensuring equitable access to Teacher Education to all educational level.

New education policy 2020 and Teacher Education:

Teacher, truly shape the future of our children and, therefore the future of our nation. It is because of the noblest role that the teacher in India was the most repeated member of society only the very best and most learned became teachers , pass on their knowledge, skills , and ethics optimally to students. The quality of teacher education recruitment, development, service conditions and empowerment of the teacher is not where it should be, and consequently the quality and motivation of the teachers does not reach the desired standard. The high respect for teacher and the high status of the teaching profession must be restored so as to inspire the best to enter the teaching profession. The motivation and empowerment of teacher is required to ensure the best possible future for our children and our nation. As per the new policy by 2030 , the minimum degree required for teaching will be a four year Integrated B.Ed .Apart from this the teacher Eligibility Test (TET) will also be changed as per the new school system The TET , will also be enrolled to cover teacher across all stage (Foundational , preparing , middle and secondary) of school education TET will also be developed according for subject teacher suitable TET or the National Testing Agency NTA test scores in the corresponding subject will hold exam for all subject and a common aptitude test . Those who quality TET will have to give a demonstration or appear in an language, as per the new policy as per the NEP." Interview will become an integral part of teacher hiring . These interview would also assess comfort and proficiency in teaching in the local language. It would be must for teacher in private schools as well to qualify TET.

The hiring and vacancies in school will managed digitally. A technology - based comprehensive teacher requirement planning forecasting excepted subject wise teacher vacancies over the next two decades.

Changes in B.Ed:

Since school will need teacher who can teach in multiple language and have knowledge of new age courses like computational thinking coding etc introduced at the school level under the NEP, B.Ed course will also be changed accordingly the B.Ed courses will be of four year duration dual B.Ed degree with a focus on one language and having bilingual lectures will be offered too education of gifted children.

One and two - year B.Ed options will also be available. Two years B.Ed will be offered only those who have completed the equivalent of four year multidisciplinary Bachelor's degree or who have obtained a master's degree. These candidate will be later hired as subject teacher in the area of specially (or the subject pursued at UG or PG level)

Additionally, shorter post B.Ed certification courses will also be made widely available, at multidisciplinary college and universities

Merit-based scholarships:

To ensure that outstanding students enter the teaching profession especially from rural areas. A large number of merit based scholarship shall be instituted across the country for studying quality 4-year integrated B.Ed programs. In rural areas Special merit-based scholarship s will be established that also include preferential employment in their local areas upon successful completion of their B.Ed programmes.

Such scholarships will provide local job opportunities to local students, especially female students so that these students serve as local-area role models and highly qualified teachers who speak the local language. Incentives will be provided for teachers to take up teaching jobs in rural areas.

Mandatory training courses:

Teachers who have already been hired will be expected to participate in at least to 50 hours of continuous professional development (CPD) every year

The merit based structure of tenure, promotion, and salary structure will be developed under this model, teachers will be incentivized. The system of assessment will consist of multiple parameters. These parameters will be developed by each state and will include peer reviews, attendance, committeemen, hours of CPD, and the community.

A common guiding set of National professional standards for Teachers (NPST) will be developed by the National council for Teacher Education. The professional standards will be reviewed every 10 years.

Teacher transfers will be halted, as per NEP2020, Transfers will be allowed in "very special circumstances "future more. Transfer will be conducted through an online computerized system that ensures transparency.

"In order to fully restore the integrity of the teacher education system ,stringent Acton will be taken against substandard stand-alone Teacher Education institutions (TETs)running In the country including shutting them down , required, as per NEP."

Suggestions:

- i. Availability of job Opportunities in various facilities for the teacher
- ii. Innovative and inspiring to overcome the frustration that has come in pedagogy in education.
- iii. All Government schools in India should be reformed and technology should be provided for quality education.

Conclusion:

Innovative Education policy2020 when it comes to teacher education, it appears that this policy is well thought out and the recruitment will be done according to the TET, NTA test But the recruitment needs to be done as soon as possible and the development of the country is certain only if the education system Which is the foundation of the country's development is strong.NEP-2020 is very important in this regard.And this does not hinder the rapid development of the country.

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